

Development of a Classification-based Eye Gaze estimation technique using an Integrated Laptop Camera: two models are better than one

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Abstract

While there are many purely software-based solutions available for live head pose tracking, the same is not true for gaze estimation which is usually done using specialised hardware; typically, eye-trackers that use infrared light sources and special camera. The challenge when using vision-based Machine Learning methods to estimate gaze from an image of a user is that the features of a user's eyes that vary with gaze position are small and difficult to track. This paper describes a classification-based Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) system that can, from images of a user's face, estimate where on a screen they are looking in real time. Labelled images of an individual looking at specified regions of a screen were collected, and these images were used to train a Deep Learning model. The final model trained was found to be accurate enough to correctly guess which section of the screen (3x3 grid) the user is looking in over 99% of the time. The current system requires strict input conditions on head orientation, a limitation on the system. The integration of head pose estimation and methods of improving resolution are discussed. The approach uses two classifiers, one for horizontal gaze (3 regions) and another for vertical gaze (3 regions) combined to estimate gaze location. This approach was found to be more effective than a single classifier for nine separate regions. Using both eyes, excluding the nose region and other facial features of the input images also improved performance.

Keywords: Gaze Estimation, Machine Learning, Machine Vision, Convolutional Neural Networks

1 Introduction

Currently, live and accurate gaze estimation is usually achieved using specialist hardware that utilizes infrared light sources and cameras to track the position of a user's corneas [\[Guestrin et al. 2006\]](#). Gaze estimation has many applications, including computer vision [\[Krafka et al. 2016\]](#), human-computer interfacing [\[Jacob et al. 2013\]](#), marketing research [\[Wedel et al. 2008\]](#) and medical diagnosis [\[Holzman et al. 1974\]](#). There is interest in the development of a gaze estimation system that is inexpensive, easy to use and does not require a high level of setup.

The upfront cost involved in purchasing this hardware, as well as the requirement to calibrate it for each user, makes it a barrier for those who wish to use it in some research or commercial applications. The less expensive face tracking alternatives that include eye tracking make use of advanced cameras, such as that of iOS Face ID. This camera utilises an infrared projector and infrared camera [\[Apple 2017\]](#).

In this work, Machine Learning was used to train a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to label the region of a screen that a user is looking at. This is done using an image of their face collected on a standard laptop webcam. CNN's are well-suited for the task of image classification. This approach requires consistent features that can be identified, tracked and correlate with the section of the screen the user is looking at. Using this approach, a purely software-based method for gaze estimation was developed that does not require structured light sources. This reduces the hardware barrier for users wishing to do gaze estimation to a PC to run the software and a webcam of sufficient resolution. An application using the gaze estimator was developed to demonstrate its utility.

Current gaze estimation software requires personal calibration by the user to accurately map their gaze. While the CNN model developed in this paper requires individual datasets to calibrate for each user, a feature of these neural networks is that, with a broad enough dataset, they can be trained to recognize features that are generalized. This means that it may be possible to make a model that requires no calibration for low resolution operation. This would require a larger training dataset consisted of a large enough group of subjects to ensure that the model does not rely on features present only in some subjects, and instead uses features that are present in most subjects.

2 State of the Art

Typically, gaze estimation is done using structured light sources (usually infrared light sources) which allow an infrared camera to triangulate the location of a user's cornea in a scene, and from the portion of the cornea that is visible estimate where on the screen the user is looking. Usually this is done with multiple infrared sources, such as with the iOS Face ID [\[Apple 2017\]](#). Commercial eye trackers also make use of specialist equipment [\[Tobii\]](#) [\[Gazepoint\]](#) which can be mounted alongside a screen to estimate eye gaze location.

While purely software-based gaze estimators that only make use of visible light cameras have been developed, in most cases this has been attempted using Support Vector Machines to track the movement of eye features [\[Papoutsaki et al. 2016\]](#) [\[Quirós et al. 2014\]](#) [\[Wu et al. 2012\]](#). This approach is limited by camera resolution and lighting conditions as the minute features of the eye and their changes over time can be difficult to track accurately outside of ideal conditions. Typically, their accuracy is lacking compared to hardware-based solutions, with typical accuracy values ranging from 65.3% to 73.6% [\[Quirós et al. 2014\]](#) or mean error of ~100 pixels [\[Papoutsaki et al. 2016\]](#), with licensed software having an accuracy of 1-1.5 degrees under ideal conditions [\[GazeSense SDK\]](#) [\[GazeRecorder\]](#). This is opposed to a mean error of ~30 pixels for typical hardware-based solutions [\[Tobii\]](#).

In recent years, attempts have been made to utilize Convolutional Neural Networks to classify images of a user's face in relation to where on a screen they are looking [\[Akinyelu et al. 2022\]](#) [\[Palmero et al. 2018\]](#). As these networks are well suited to the problems of machine vision and image classification, there are high expectations for their applications in gaze estimation. In practice, most implementations do not control for head orientation and instead try to make their models head orientation invariant. Most CNN models are trained using either full-face images [\[Akinyelu et al. 2022\]](#) or at least a band of the image spanning from one eye to the other, including the middle of the user's face [\[Palmero et al. 2018\]](#). Additionally, these tasks are usually approached as a regression problem instead of a classification problem, assigning continuous coordinate values to images instead of classifying it to a discreet location.

This paper outlines a novel, classification-based approach to the problem of gaze estimation. The paper also explores improvements that can be made to the techniques currently in use by examining the feature maps the models produce. Preprocessing the image, by extraction of eye regions, as well as utilizing multiple models was shown to improve the overall accuracy

3 System Development

The models trained were developed using the TensorFlow Python module [\[TensorFlow\]](#) using a dataset collected over the course of development. The final system overview is outlined in Figure 1.

Training code was developed to allow the collection of a dataset of labelled images of the user looking at regions of the screen. The user was asked to gaze at highlighted horizontal or vertical regions of the screen displayed using the PyGame module [\[PyGame\]](#) and hold down spacebar for the duration. For each frame of video recorded, a series of Haar Cascade Classifiers from the OpenCV library [\[OpenCV\]](#) were used to identify the regions of the image

likely to contain an eye. These regions were then extracted and combined to form a single image. This image contained images of the left and right eye stitched together. These steps were then repeated until enough labelled images were collected for each region of the screen.

Figure 1: System Overview

These images were then used to train a Convolutional Neural Network for horizontal and vertical classification using the TensorFlow Keras library [Tensorflow]. Training was run until a sufficient accuracy rate and error rate was achieved. This was done by separating a subset of the image dataset into a validation set on which the models' accuracy and error rate was tested.

Finally, a live video feed was taken from the webcam, and for each frame read in the eye sections were isolated from the image as done during the dataset collection. Using inference, the horizontal and vertical models were then used to make a prediction of the label assigned to these new images. The models' best guess at the gaze location in the 3x3 grid is then displayed on the screen in real time, with guesses being made every ~0.5 seconds.

Most CNN techniques estimate a users' gaze using a single CNN model [Akinyelu et al. 2022] [Palmero et al. 2018]. This regressively computes a function to assign a continuous x and y value of gaze location, given an image of a user's face. This paper took a different approach, in that the screen was split into discrete segments for the user to look within. The models produced then classify images of the user's face with a discrete value for each segment. The model structure and techniques used mirrored those commonly used in previous papers, however changes were made that were found to significantly improve the accuracy of the models and the performance of the system overall.

The first design change made was to pre-emptively remove unnecessary sections of training images on which models were incorrectly identifying features. This was done after the feature maps generated by the models were examined. It was found that many of the misclassified images had features identified on the user's face or outside their eyes, effectively training on noise. To reduce this issue, the training images were cropped to only include a band spanning from one eye to the other. When it was found that the model was still identifying features around the user's nose, the middle section between the eyes was then cut out to reduce the input training images to just the two eye sections stitched together, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Example of the input image and feature maps produced by 3 different models. (a) input image, (b) activation map generated by a single 3x3 model. (c) activation map generated by 1x3 model focused on determining vertical position. (d) activation map generated by 3x1 model focused on determining horizontal position. White pixels represent pixels of significance. Note for (c) and (d) the areas of significance around the sclera of the pupil, and the lack of weighting on other, irrelevant features.

The second change made was moving to a multi-model system for classifying the images instead of using a single model. During development, it was found that the feature maps for input images had trouble identifying both features that help discern the horizontal position and the vertical position of the user's gaze at the same time. To reduce this issue, the tasks were split between two models. One model focused entirely on discerning the horizontal gaze location and the other on the vertical location. This was found to improve the overall accuracy of the system from an accuracy of between 65% and 75% to between 99.3% and 100%. While this had the consequence of nearly doubling the training time for each system. Since the time needed for a model to produce a guess for an input image once it has been trained is approximately 0.04 - 0.05 seconds, doubling this prediction time had no noticeable effect for the end user of the software.

Figure 3: A diagram illustrating how the combination of a 3x1 and a 1x3 model is equivalent to a single 3x3 model.

Finally, the software was adapted into an application to demonstrate the feasibility of the tool being developed into an API. The application allowed users to make a hot beverage using only their gaze (choice) and a single key (accept). The purpose of this application was to highlight how a gaze estimator could be used, especially by those with limited mobility, to interact with computers. Another simple application was made that displayed images of two similar products and tracked which product the user looked at (if either) in each frame. The purpose of this code was to demonstrate one possible commercial application of the gaze estimation software in product design and marketing, see Figure 4.

Figure 4: (a), (b) eye tracking demonstration. The blue segment represents the best guess of gaze region on screen. The location of the red dot (eye gaze) is found using the models' confidence levels for each section, to show a more accurate location than the system's actual resolution (3x3). (c) shows application demonstration.

All software developed can be found at: <https://github.com/JackCribbin/Gaze-Estimation-CNN>

4 Results

The accuracy of models developed was validated using a dataset of images separate to the ones used to train the models. The models were then live tested, however data was not collected for this testing as it was simply to validate the general accuracy of the models and check for possible mislabelling of training images. Figure 5 shows a graph of accuracy and loss for the horizontal model developed. As can be seen, accuracy rises sharply before plateauing at a value between 99.3% and 100%, whereas loss drops sharply and plateaus at a value between 1.6% and 1.8%.

Figure 5: Plots of Model Accuracy and Loss for two example model trainings, one with 15 epochs (left) and one with 50 epochs (right). Model training was stopped when accuracy plateaued to avoid overtraining, which would make the models less elastic and worsen performance on new, unseen images.

This accuracy is limited to a resolution of $1/9^{\text{th}}$ of the screen as the screen was split into 3×3 segments while collecting the datasets. Thus, the gaze estimator developed has an accuracy of over 99% within a region of 9.9 cm by 5.6 cm on a 29.7 cm by 16.7 cm screen at a typical viewing distance of approximately 40 cm.

However, this resolution is not necessarily an upper limit, it is simply the highest resolution tested by this paper. Further work may increase the dual models to two 4×1 models to reduce the segment size to $1/16^{\text{th}}$ of the screen. Additionally, by making use of classification confidence levels, a specific point of gaze can be estimated within or between segments. This is done by using the models' confidence levels for multiple segments and multiplying these by the distance from the centre of the screen to show a more accurate guess than the system's actual resolution. See the red dot on Figure 4(a).

5 Future Work

Current work aims to train new models to improve the resolution and reduce the size of the segments the models use to classify images.

Additionally, integrating data on the user's head position and orientation during training for each image may reduce the limitations on the user to hold a fixed pose while the software is being used. This could be done by using a Support Vector Machine-based head tracker to produce pitch, yaw and roll data which would be included in the training data alongside the images.

Finally, additional datasets could be collected from various individuals to test the efficacy of a generalised gaze estimator that does not require individual calibration.

6 Conclusions

This paper demonstrates a method to estimate a user's gaze using only an integrated laptop camera and classification-based Convolutional Neural Network models. Adjustments were made to standard practices currently implemented to improve performance, such as approaching the task as a classification problem, limiting input data to solely relevant regions and making use of two models instead of one. The models developed serve as a proof of concept for the viability of developing a calibration-necessary, software-based gaze estimator, with single user accuracy above 99% within a resolution of $1/9^{\text{th}}$ of the screen achieved after calibration. Future work with larger and more varied datasets from multiple users will show if the features identified for individuals can be generalised to produce a model that does not require calibration for each user.

References:

- [Guestrin and Eizenman, 2006] Guestrin, E.D. and Eizenman, M., 2006. General theory of remote gaze estimation using the pupil center and corneal reflections. *IEEE Transactions on biomedical engineering*, 53(6), pp.1124-1133. Available at: <https://vemlab.github.io/127.0.0.1/static/attachment/36.pdf>
- [Krafka et al., 2016] Krafka, K., Khosla, A., Kellnhofer, P., Kannan, H., Bhandarkar, S., Matusik, W. and Torralba, A., 2016. Eye tracking for everyone. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 2176-2184). Available at: https://www.cvfoundation.org/openaccess/content_cvpr_2016/html/Krafka_Eye_Tracking_for_CVPR_2016_paper.html
- [Jacob and Karn, 2013] Jacob, R.J. and Karn, K.S., 2003. Eye tracking in human-computer interaction and usability research: Ready to deliver the promises. In *The mind's eye* (pp. 573-605). North-Holland. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780444510204500311?via%3Dihub>
- [Wedel and Pieters, 2008] Wedel, M. and Pieters, R., 2008. Eye tracking for visual marketing. *Foundations and Trends® in Marketing*, 1(4), pp.231-320. Available at: <https://www.nowpublishers.com/article/Details/MKT-011>
- [Holzman et al., 1974] Holzman, P.S., Proctor, L.R., Levy, D.L., Yasillo, N.J., Meltzer, H.Y. and Hurt, S.W., 1974. Eye-tracking dysfunctions in schizophrenic patients and their relatives. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 31(2), pp.143-151. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4851993/>
- [Apple 2017] Apple Inc. (2017) Apple awards Finisar \$390 million from its Advanced Manufacturing Fund, 13 December, 2017. Available at: <https://www.apple.com/newsroom/2017/12/apple-awards-finisar-390-million-from-its-advanced-manufacturing-fund/>
- [Tobii] Tobii, <https://www.tobii.com/products/eye-trackers>, accessed on 12/06/2023
- [GazePoint] GazePoint, <https://www.gazept.com/shop>, accessed on 12/06/2023
- [Quirós and Cristina, 2014] Cabrera Quirós, L.C., 2014. Eye gaze estimation using SVM for regression from face and eye detection results (Doctoral dissertation). Available at: <http://repositorio.conicit.go.cr:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/88>
- [Wu et al., 2012] Wu, Y.L., Yeh, C.T., Hung, W.C. and Tang, C.Y., 2014. Gaze direction estimation using support vector machine with active appearance model. *Multimedia tools and applications*, 70, pp.2037-2062. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257627330_Gaze_direction_estimation_using_support_vector_mach_in_e_with_active_appearance_model
- [Papoutsaki et al. 2016] Papoutsaki, A., Sangkloy, P., Laskey, J., Daskalova, N., Huang, J. and Hays, J. 2016. WebGazer: Scalable Webcam Eye Tracking Using User Interactions. 25th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence. Available at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305375498_WebGazer_Scalable_Webcam_Eye_Tracking_Using_User_Interactions/references

[GazeSense SDK] GazeSense SDK, eyeware, <https://eyeware.tech/gazesense-eye-tracking-software-for-webcams-3d-sensor>, accessed on 12/06/2023

[GazeRecorder] GazeRecorder, <https://gazerecorder.com/webcam-eye-tracking-accuracy>, accessed on 12/06/2023

[Akinyelu and Blignaut, 2022] Akinyelu, A.A. and Blignaut, P., 2022. Convolutional Neural Network-Based Technique for Gaze Estimation on Mobile Devices. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 4, p.796825. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frai.2021.796825/full>

[Palmero et al., 2018] Palmero, C., Selva, J., Bagheri, M.A. and Escalera, S., 2018. Recurrent cnn for 3d gaze estimation using appearance and shape cues. arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.03064. Available at: <http://www.bmva.org/bmvc/2018/contents/papers/0871.pdf>

[TensorFlow] TensorFlow, <https://tensorflow.org>, accessed on 12/06/2023

[OpenCV] OpenCV, <https://opencv.org>, accessed on 12/06/2023

[Pygame] Pygame, <https://pygame.org>, accessed on 12/06/2023